

Towards fucose-based glycomimetics targeting DC-SIGN: Fucosylation strategies, synthesis and binding studies of model compounds

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Abstract

DC-SIGN, a C-type lectin receptor expressed on immune cells, is considered a promising target for immunomodulatory and antiviral therapies. While mannose-based glycomimetics have been extensively studied as DC-SIGN ligands, fucose-based strategies remain underexplored. This study explores the fucosylation of linear alcohols and sugars using eight different fucosyl donors, aiming at designing strategies for the development of fucose-based glycomimetics targeting DC-SIGN. Four types of leaving groups and two different acyl-based protecting groups on the donors were tested. The glycosylation of 3-azidopropan-1-ol exclusively yielded the β -anomer, demonstrating high stereoselectivity. The azido group in the product is versatile, allowing for direct click chemistry reactions or reduction to an amine for further functionalization. Both types of reactions were demonstrated in a model reaction. In the glycosylation of a sugar, a disaccharide moiety of Lewis X

antigen was selected as a target molecule. Only one of the eight tested fucosyl donors worked well in this reaction and provided the product in a reasonable yield. The disaccharide was also equipped with the 3-azidopropyl linker, facilitating future modifications. Finally, NMR studies confirmed compatibility of the linker with canonical Ca^{2+} -dependent carbohydrate binding to DC-SIGN, suggesting potential for further development of fucose-based glycomimetics targeting this C-type lectin receptor.

Keywords

L-fucose, glycomimetics, glycosylation, Lewis X, DC-SIGN, NMR

Graphical abstract

1. Introduction

DC-SIGN (dendritic cell-specific intercellular adhesion molecule-3-grabbing non-integrin) is a C-type lectin receptor primarily expressed on dendritic cells, certain macrophages and T cells.^{1, 2} It plays a pivotal role in the immune system by mediating cell adhesion, immune modulation, and pathogen recognition. DC-SIGN is crucial for recognizing a broad range of pathogens, including viruses (e.g., HIV, SARS-CoV2, Dengue), bacteria, and fungi, through its binding to carbohydrate structures on their surfaces.³⁻⁶ Taking into account various roles of DC-SIGN in immunity and infection, DC-SIGN ligands are interesting for their potential use in antiviral and anti-inflammatory therapies, cancer immunotherapy as well as in the development of more efficient vaccines.^{7, 8}

Natural DC-SIGN ligands are primarily high-mannose oligosaccharides and fucosylated glycans, such as the Lewis X (Le^x , $\text{Gal}\beta4[\text{Fuc}\alpha3]\text{GlcNAc}$) antigen. It binds these oligosaccharides in a multivalent Ca^{2+} -dependent manner. The prospect of using such complex structures clinically is low because of their complicated synthesis or isolation from natural sources and possible off-target effects. In recent years, the focus has been predominantly on developing various mannose-based glycomimetics,⁹⁻¹⁴ while fucosides have gained only little attention.¹⁵⁻¹⁸

Mannosylated inhibitors can interact with various lectin receptors, such as the mannose receptor, langerin, dectin-2, Endo-180, and many others, leading to undesired side effects.¹⁹ Fucose-based molecules, however, demonstrate a greater tendency to exclusively target DC-SIGN, potentially minimizing unwanted interactions with other lectin receptors.²⁰ This enhanced selectivity could translate to fewer side effects in therapeutic applications and a shorter path to selective inhibitors.²⁰ Le^x, also known as cluster of differentiation 15 (CD 15) or stage-specific embryonic antigen 1 (SSEA-1), is a branched trisaccharide composed of L-fucose (Fuc), N-acetyl-D-glucosamine (GlcNAc), and D-galactose (Gal) (Fig. 1a). It is found in various glycoconjugates, including those present on human immune cells. Le^x overexpression is also observed on the surface of certain tumour cells, such as in breast and colorectal cancers, where it functions as an adhesion molecule.^{21, 22} This makes it a useful biomarker for tumour progression, metastasis, and patient prognosis. Furthermore, Le^x-containing glycans have been identified on pathogens like *Schistosoma mansoni* and *Helicobacter pylori*, potentially facilitating their interaction with DC-SIGN.^{23, 24}

Ultimately aiming at developing new fucose-based glycomimetics as DC-SIGN ligands, we first decided to explore the reactivity of fucose in a fucosylation reaction, both with an aliphatic alcohol and another sugar moiety. Fucosides bearing aliphatic linker (such as target compound **1**, Fig. 1b) could be used in various glycan arrays as well as in coating the surface of nanoparticles for active drug delivery. As a model compound for the study of fucosylation of a carbohydrate moiety, we chose to prepare the disaccharide motif Fuc(1-3)GlcNAc (**2**, Fig. 1b) from Lewis X. To make this disaccharide useful similarly as alkyl fucoside **1**, we equipped it with an aliphatic linker.

While L-fucose occurs in nature predominantly as α -glycoside, achieving this specific linkage presents a significant challenge. In 2001, Vermeer et al. in his study on fucosylation of linear alcohols observed little stereoselectivity of fucosylation with 2-O-benzyl-protected donors.²⁵ All reactions led to a mixture of anomers. While the naturally occurring α -anomer is necessary for many applications studying natural products, in many cases, when the interaction occurs far from the anomeric site, a β -anomer can be equally useful. Bearing this in mind and knowing that fucose interacts with DC-SIGN *via* its 3- and 4-OH groups,¹⁷ we chose to work with peracetylated and perbenzoylated donors, which are easy to prepare and to deprotect, and set off to investigate the anomeric selectivity and the reaction yields.

Fig. 1: Structures of a) Lewis X and fucose, b) target compounds **1** and **2**, and c) L-fucosyl donors **3–10**.

2. Results and discussion

2.1 Synthesis

We set off to evaluate common types of fucosyl donors (Fig. 1c): esters (**3**, **4**), trichloroacetimidates (**5**, **6**), thioglycosides (**7**, **8**), and bromides (**9**, **10**) with respect to their reactivity and anomeric selectivity. The donors were prepared following standard procedures (refer to Supporting Information). Thioglycosides **7** and **8** showed some unusual signal splitting in their ¹H NMR spectra, and we therefore performed a detailed NMR study to confirm their structure and the origin of the splitting (see Section 2.2).

To study fucosylation of linear alcohols (Scheme 1), we chose 3-azidopropan-1-ol (**11**) as acceptor. The versatility of the azido group will enable the obtained alkyl fucosides to be attached to solid support or any other moiety either directly using a copper-catalyzed azide–alkyne cycloaddition (CuAAC), or indirectly *via* an amide coupling after its reduction to an amino group.

For each donor, we first used reaction conditions common for the particular donor type, and if the yields were not satisfactory, we further optimized them. For direct glycosylation using peracetylated and perbenzoylated donors **3** and **4**, BF₃·OEt₂ was used as an activator. It was added at –5 °C and the reaction mixture was then stirred overnight at room temperature. Although the β-anomer was obtained exclusively, glycosylation products **12** and **13** were obtained in unsatisfactory yields of 7% and 21%, respectively. Trichloroacetimidates **5** and **6** were activated with TMSOTf, which was added at –15 °C; the reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min and then warmed up to room temperature and stirred for another 30 min. Thioglycoside donors **7** and **8** were activated by NIS and TfOH and the reaction proceeded at –5 °C. Finally, we tried glycosylation using fucosyl bromides **9** and **10**, using Ag₂O and TfOH for activation. All glycosylations were performed in dry DCM (using donors **3–8**) or dry toluene (donors **9** and **10**) in the presence of activated 4 Å molecular sieves and under inert

atmosphere. While donors (**5–9**) provided the desired products in the yield of 40–60%, benzoyl-protected bromide **10** stood out with the yield of 80%. Reaction conditions and yields are summarized in Table 1. In general, benzoyl-protected donors gave higher yields than their acetylated counterparts. Surprisingly, only the β -anomer ($J = 7.9$ Hz) was obtained in all the cases. The anomeric configuration of the obtained product was confirmed from NOE NMR spectra (Fig. S1).

Subsequently, the protecting groups were removed under the Zemplén conditions (0.2 M sodium methoxide solution in dry methanol) to provide target alkyl fucoside **1**. Corresponding amine **14** was prepared by treating azide **1** with Pd/C under hydrogen atmosphere (Scheme 1). Although product **14** was obtained in high purity after reversed-phase column purification, it was highly unstable and decomposed over time, even if stored at -20 °C. On the contrary, azide **1** was stable both under the storage conditions and in solution.

In order to verify the reactivity of our fucoside in a CuAAC reaction, we ran a model reaction of azide **1** with propargyl amine. The reaction was catalyzed by $\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2$ and proceeded in the presence of sodium ascorbate in a mixture of *tert*-butyl alcohol and water (1:1) at room temperature (Scheme 1). Compound **15** was obtained in a 61% yield and was stable in solution.

Scheme 1: a) Glycosylation of 3-azidopropan-1-ol (**11**) using different fucosyl donors (**3–10**). b) Further modification of azide **1**: reduction of the azido group and CuAAC reaction with propargyl amine.

Table 1: Glycosylation of 3-azidopropan-1-ol (**11**) using fucosyl donors **3–10**.

Donor	LG	Solvent	Conditions	Product	Yield
3	OAc	DCM	1. BF ₃ ·OEt ₂ , -5 °C, 30 min 2. r.t., 16 h	12	7%
4	OBz	DCM	1. BF ₃ ·OEt ₂ , -5 °C, 30 min 2. r.t., 16 h	13	21%
5	OC(NH)CCl ₃	DCM	1. TMSOTf, -15 °C, 30 min 2. r.t., 30 min	12	47%
6	OC(NH)CCl ₃	DCM	1. TMSOTf, -15 °C, 30 min 2. r.t., 30 min	13	80%
7	SEt	DCM	1. NIS, TfOH, -5 °C, 90 min 2. r.t., 15 min	12	46%
8	SEt	DCM	1. NIS, TfOH, -5 °C, 90 min 2. r.t., 15 min	13	49%
9	Br	Toluene	1. Ag ₂ O, r.t., 10 min 2. TfOH, 0 °C, 10 min 3. r.t., 10 min	12	43%
10	Br	Toluene	1. Ag ₂ O, r.t., 10 min 2. TfOH, 0 °C, 10 min 3. r.t., 10 min	13	58%

Our next goal was to study the reactivity of fucosyl donors **3–10** with a carbohydrate acceptor. Aiming to prepare the disaccharide moiety of Lewis X, we first needed to synthesize the respective protected and alkylated *N*-acetyl-D-glucosamine acceptor **16**. It was prepared in five steps in a 32% overall yield (refer to Supporting Information).

Fucosylation of carbohydrate acceptor **16** (Scheme 2) turned out to be more challenging than expected. For each donor **3–10**, we initially used the reaction conditions optimized for aliphatic alcohols (*vide supra*). However, the desired product was not obtained in any of the eight reactions. We therefore tested several different temperatures (Table S1), but without success. Eventually, we performed the glycosylation reaction with each donor starting at -78 °C and slowly warmed the reaction mixture up to room temperature. Among all tested fucosyl donors, only thioglycoside **8** provided disaccharide **18** in a reasonable yield (41%). This observation is in line with available literature – most describe syntheses of Lewis X and its derivatives use thiofucoside²⁶⁻²⁹ or fucosyl fluoride³⁰⁻³² donors. Moreover, they often describe problems with stereoselectivity or regioselectivity,^{29, 32, 33} while we obtained exclusively our desired product.

The fucosylation reaction was followed by subsequent cleavage of the benzylidene and benzoyl protecting groups to provide target azide **2**. The azide group was then reduced in a palladium-catalyzed

hydrogenation (Scheme 2). Amine **19** was obtained in a 30% yield, but, similarly to the above-discussed alkyl fucoside, turned out to be unstable in solution.

Scheme 2: Fucosylation of carbohydrate acceptor **16**. Synthesis of target disaccharide **2**.

2.2 NMR structural analysis

When preparing thioglycosides **7** and **8**, we observed unusual signal splitting in their ^1H NMR spectra (Fig. 2a). Unlike in many other ethyl thioglycosides, the two protons belonging to the S-CH₂ group appear as non-equivalent and the signal corresponding to them is a complex multiplet. Furthermore, while in **7**, the anomeric signal was an expected doublet ($J = 9.9$ Hz), in **8**, it appeared as a multiplet because of a long-distance interaction. This prompted us to try to separate the anomers and eventually we obtained pure acetylated β -ethylthiofucoside **7** and benzoylated α -ethylthiofucoside **8**. The two compounds were fully characterized by ^1H , ^{13}C APT, HSQC, and HMBC spectra. NOE experiments were used to confirm the anomeric configuration. In compound **7**, NOE between H1, H3 and H5 confirmed the β configuration (Fig. S2), while in compound **8**, NOE between H1 and H2, and between S-CH₂ and H5 confirmed the α configuration (Fig. S3).

Fig. 2: a) Excerpt from ^1H NMR spectra of compounds β -7 and α -8 with details of signal splitting, b) anomeric signal (H1) in compounds **13**, **1**, and **14**, c) long-range COSY to confirm a long-range interaction between H1 and H4 in compound **14**.

Since fucosylation is not always stereoselective and we cannot rely on neighbouring group participation, it was necessary to determine the anomeric configuration of the obtained alkyl fucosides. For that reason, we selected fucoside **13** and conducted NOE experiments (Fig. S1). We observed a strong NOE between H1, H3 and H5, consistent with the β -anomer. The absence of NOE between H1 and H4 further confirmed the β -anomer.

Finally, we used fucoside **14** to explain the unusual splitting pattern (Fig. 2b) of the anomeric signal in compounds **1** and **14**. COSY experiment showed interaction of H1 with H2 and H3 and a long-range COSY (Ir-COSY) experiment detected coupling of H1 with H4 (Fig. 2c).

2.3 Affinity for DC-SIGN

Aiming at establishing a method for designing fucose-based glycomimetics selectively binding to DC-SIGN, we compared the binding site and affinity of the stable alkyl fucosides **1**, **15** and **2** to the **Fuc** monosaccharide in ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC NMR titration experiments with the ^{15}N labelled DC-SIGN carbohydrate recognition domain (CRD).

Both alkyl-monosaccharides **1** and **15** yielded chemical shift perturbations (CSPs) on the ^1H - ^{15}N backbone resonances of DC-SIGN CRD similar to **Fuc** (Fig. S4a,b). As expected, the strongest CSPs were observed in resonances of residues around the carbohydrate binding site at Ca^{2+} site II (E347, N349, N350) and β strands β 3 and β 4 (E358, S360, N365, D366, D367), suggesting preservation of the Ca^{2+} -dependent binding mode for the alkyl fucosides (Fig. 3b,c; Fig. S5b,c; and Fig. S6b,c).^{34,35} Likewise, the CSP map of the alkyl disaccharide **2** suggested Ca^{2+} dependent binding similar to **Fuc** (Fig S4c). However, several resonances of residues involved in binding of **2** (N349, V351, D355, N365, D366) displayed severe line broadening, indicative of intermediate exchange phenomena (Fig. S7b,c,d).³⁶ This was only observed for residue D366 upon addition of the alkyl-monosaccharides **1** and **15** and not for **Fuc**, suggesting higher affinity of the alkyl-disaccharide.

To quantify affinities, we selected CSP trajectories exhibiting fast exchange under increasing ligand concentrations and estimated their dissociation constants (K_D) (Fig. 3d,e; Fig. S5d,e; Fig. S6d,e; and Fig. S7d,e). The alkyl monosaccharides **1** ($K_D = 3.6 \pm 0.6$ mM) and **15** ($K_D = 3.7 \pm 0.9$ mM) showed affinities comparable to **Fuc** ($K_D = 4.4 \pm 1.0$ mM), consistent with previously reported values.³⁴ Titration of **2** ($K_D = 1.7 \pm 1.2$ mM) yielded approximately 2-fold higher affinity compared to the monosaccharides. This increase in affinity of the alkyl-disaccharide was found to be in the range of previously reported oligosaccharides interacting with DC-SIGN.^{34, 35}

Figure 3: Interaction of **1** with DC-SIGN CRD. a) Superimposed ^1H – ^{15}N HSQC NMR titration spectra of ^{15}N -labelled DC-SIGN CRD interacting with varying concentrations of **1** reveal several concentration-dependent CSPs. b) and c) Mapping of CSPs induced at 3.125 mM **1** to the structure of DC-SIGN CRD (PDB code: 1SL4), suggest the ligand to interact with the carbohydrate binding site around Ca^{2+} site II in the long loop region and beta strands $\beta 3$ and $\beta 4$. Line broadening beyond detection is indicated by blue spheres and blue bars in b) and c), respectively. Unassigned residues are highlighted in grey. d) Examples of residues in the carbohydrate binding site showing fast exchanging resonances upon titration. e) Fitting of CSPs over varying concentrations of **1** enabled approximation of the affinity of the interaction ($K_D = 3.6 \pm 0.6$ mM).

3. Conclusion

Fucose-based glycomimetics show significant potential as efficient DC-SIGN ligands, demonstrating higher selectivity compared to their mannose-based counterparts.¹⁵ These compounds hold promise for applications in immunomodulatory and antiviral therapies. This study aimed to explore the fucosylation of aliphatic alcohols and sugars and evaluate the influence of aliphatic linker on DC-SIGN binding. The synthetic part focused on examining the effects of the leaving group and protecting groups on reaction outcomes. Among the eight fucosyl donors tested, benzoyl-protected fucosyl bromide emerged as the most efficient donor for the fucosylation of the tested aliphatic alcohol. All eight donors consistently yielded the β -anomer of target alkyl fucoside as confirmed by NOE analysis.

For the fucosylation of sugars, only the benzoylated thioglycoside donor proved effective. The versatility of the azido group was demonstrated through successful conversion to an amine *via* catalytic reduction and its application in CuAAC reaction, underscoring its utility for further functionalization. Detailed NMR studies of thioglycoside donors and alkyl fucoside **13** elucidated the origin of unexpected splitting patterns in the ^1H NMR spectra. NMR studies of the alkyl fucosides interacting with DC-SIGN CRD pointed towards preservation of the canonical Ca^{2+} -dependent binding mode. These results suggest that the alkyl linker does not interfere with the interaction at the carbohydrate binding site, supporting the potential of these derivatives for further exploration in DC-SIGN targeting applications.

4. Experimental section

4.1 General

All reagents and starting materials were purchased from commercial sources and used without further purification. The solvents were purified and dried using standard procedures.³⁷ Preparative column chromatography was performed on Kieselgel 60 0.040–0.063 mm (Merck). TLC analyses were carried out on DC Alufolien Kieselgel 60 F254 (Merck). The TLC plates were visualized with a sugar stain solution (5% H_2SO_4 , 0.5% 3-methoxyphenol in EtOH). Reversed-phase separations were performed on C18 Sep-Pak 6cc (Waters) 1 g cartridges. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were measured on Agilent 400-MR DDR2 and JEOL-ECZL400G at 25 °C. Chemical shifts (δ) are reported in parts per million (ppm) relative to the respective residual solvent peaks (CDCl_3 : δ 7.26 in ^1H and δ 77.16 in ^{13}C ; CD_3OD δ 3.31 in ^1H and δ 49.00 in ^{13}C and H_2O δ 4.79 in ^1H). The following abbreviations are used to indicate peak multiplicities: *s* singlet, *br s* broad singlet, *d* doublet, *dd* doublet of doublets, *ddd* doublet of doublets of doublets, *t* triplet, *q* quartet, *p* pentet, *dt* doublet of triplets, *td* triplet of doublets, *m* multiplet. The coupling constants (*J*) are reported in hertz (Hz). NMR spectra were evaluated using MestreNova 14.1.1 (Mestrelab Research SSL). Both low- and high-resolution mass spectra MS were obtained by using electrospray ionization (ESI). The spectra were measured on LTQ Orbitrap XL (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

4.2 Fucosylation of an aliphatic alcohol

4.2.1 2,3,4-Tri-*O*-acetyl-1-*O*-(3-azidopropyl)- β -L-fucopyranoside (**12**)

Procedure A: Tetra-*O*-acetyl-L-fucopyranose (**3**, 100 mg, 301 μmol) was dried by co-evaporation with dry toluene (2×5 mL) and then was dried *in vacuo* for 30 min. Dry DCM (5 mL) was added and then the flask was purged with argon for 5 min. 4 Å Activated molecular sieves (50 mg) and 3-azidopropan-1-ol (**11**, 35 μL , 376 μmol) were added and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 45 min. Then it was cooled to 0 °C, $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{OEt}_2$ (0.191 mL, 1.51 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 10 min. The reaction mixture was warmed to room temperature and stirred for

16 h. The reaction mixture was poured into a saturated solution of NaHCO₃ (20 mL) and extracted with DCM (1 × 25 mL). The organic layer was washed successively with 1 M aq. NaOH (1 × 20 mL) and water (1 × 25 mL), dried over Na₂SO₄ and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated *in vacuo* to provide a crude product. The crude product was purified using column chromatography, eluting with 0% to 20% EtOAc in hexane to provide product **12** as a pale yellow syrup (8 mg, 7%). β-Anomer was obtained exclusively.

Procedure B: 2,3,4-Tri-*O*-acetyl-α-L-fucopyranosyl trichloroacetimidate (**5**, 100 mg, 230 μmol) was dried by co-evaporation with dry toluene (2 × 5 mL) and then was dried *in vacuo* for 30 min. Dry DCM (5 mL) was added and then the flask was purged with argon for 5 min. 4 Å Activated molecular sieves (50 mg) and 3-azidopropan-1-ol (**11**, 29 mg, 283 μmol) were added and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 30 min. Then it was cooled to -15 °C and TMSOTf (51 μL, 283 μmol) was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was stirred at -15 °C for 30 min and then at room temperature for 30 min. The reaction was quenched with Et₃N (0.2 mL), the mixture was filtered and the filtrate was concentrated *in vacuo* to provide a crude product. The crude product was purified by column chromatography, eluting with 0 to 20% EtOAc in hexane to provide product **12** as a light brown syrup (40 mg, 47%). β-Anomer was obtained exclusively.

Procedure C: Ethyl 2,3,4-tri-*O*-acetyl-1-thio-L-fucopyranoside (**7**, 100 mg, 299 μmol) was dried by co-evaporation with dry toluene (2 × 5 mL) and then was dried *in vacuo* for 30 min. The dried compound was dissolved in dry DCM (5 mL) and the flask was purged with argon for 5 min. 4 Å Activated molecular sieves (50 mg) and 3-azidopropan-1-ol (**11**, 45 mg, 449 μmol) were added and the solution was stirred at room temperature for 30 min. The reaction mixture was cooled to -10 °C. NIS (101 mg, 449 μmol) and trifluoromethanesulfonic acid (4.0 μL, 44.9 μmol) were added and the reaction mixture was stirred at -10 °C for 1.5 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to warm to room temperature and was diluted with DCM (20 mL). The reaction was quenched with a saturated solution of Na₂S₂O₃ (5 mL) and filtered. The layers were separated, and the organic layer was washed successively with a saturated solution of NaHCO₃ (20 mL), water (25 mL), and brine (20 mL). The organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated *in vacuo* to provide a crude product. The crude product was purified by column chromatography, eluting with 0 to 25% EtOAc in hexane to provide product **12** as a pale yellow syrup (55 mg, 47%). β-Anomer was obtained exclusively.

Procedure D: 2,3,4-Tri-*O*-acetyl-α-L-fucopyranosylbromide (**9**, 134 mg, 379 μmol) was dried by co-evaporation with dry toluene (3 × 5 mL) and then was dried *in vacuo* for 30 min. To the dried compound, dry toluene (5 mL) was added and the flask was purged with argon for 5 min. 4 Å Activated molecular sieves (50 mg) and 3-azidopropan-1-ol (**11**, 39 mg, 379 μmol) were added and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h. Then Ag₂O (88 mg, 379 μmol) was added and a black precipitate formed immediately. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 10 min. The reaction was cooled to 0 °C, trifluoromethanesulfonic acid (17 μL, 190 μmol) was added dropwise and the

reaction mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 10 min. The reaction was quenched with Et₃N (0.2 mL) and the mixture was filtered through celite, which was then thoroughly washed with DCM (2 × 25 mL). The filtrate was washed with water (2 × 25 mL). The organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated *in vacuo* to provide a crude product. The crude product was purified by column chromatography, eluting with 0 to 32% EtOAc in hexane to provide product **12** as a pale yellow syrup (61 mg, 43%). β-Anomer was obtained exclusively.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 5.24 (dd, *J* = 3.5, 1.1 Hz, 1H), 5.18 (dd, *J* = 10.5, 7.9 Hz, 1H), 5.01 (dd, *J* = 10.5, 3.4 Hz, 1H), 4.43 (d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 1H), 4.05 – 3.94 (m, 1H), 3.87 – 3.74 (m, 1H), 3.65 – 3.54 (m, 1H), 3.50 – 3.27 (m, 2H), 2.18 (s, 3H), 2.07 (s, 3H), 1.99 (s, 3H), 1.94 – 1.79 (m, 2H), 1.23 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 170.8, 170.4, 169.7, 101.3, 71.4, 70.3, 69.3, 69.1, 66.4, 48.1, 29.1, 20.9 (2C), 20.8, 16.2. MS (ESI⁺): calculated for C₁₅H₂₃N₃O₈Na⁺ 396.1 [M+Na]⁺; found *m/z* (%): 396.1 (100) [M+Na]⁺. HRMS (ESI⁺): calculated for C₁₅H₂₃N₃O₈Na⁺ 396.1377, found 396.1378 [M+Na]⁺.

4.2.2 2,3,4-Tri-*O*-benzoyl-1-*O*-(3-azidopropyl)-β-L-fucopyranoside (**13**)

Procedure A: Tetra-*O*-benzoyl-α-L-fucopyranose (**4**, 100 mg, 172 μmol) was dried by co-evaporation with dry toluene (2 × 5 mL) and then was dried *in vacuo* for 30 min. Dry DCM (5 mL) was added and then the flask was purged with argon for 5 min. 4 Å Activated molecular sieves (50 mg) and 3-azidopropan-1-ol (**11**, 20 μL, 215 μmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 45 min. Next, the reaction mixture was cooled to 0 °C, BF₃·OEt₂ (0.191 mL, 860 μmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 10 min. The reaction mixture was warmed to room temperature and stirred for 24 h. The reaction mixture was poured into a saturated solution of NaHCO₃ (20 mL) and extracted with DCM (1 × 25 mL). The organic layer was washed with 1 M aq. NaOH (1 × 20 mL) and water (1 × 25 mL), dried over Na₂SO₄ and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated *in vacuo* to provide a crude product. The crude product was purified by column chromatography, eluting with 0 to 20% EtOAc in hexane to provide product **13** as a pale yellow syrup (21 mg, 22%). β-Anomer was obtained exclusively.

Procedure B: 2,3,4-Tri-*O*-benzoyl-L-fucopyranosyl trichloroacetimidate (**6**, 100 mg, 0.161 mmol) was dried by co-evaporation with dry toluene (2 × 5 mL) and then was dried *in vacuo* for 30 min. Dry DCM (5 mL) was added and then the flask was purged with argon for 5 min. 4 Å Activated molecular sieves (50 mg) and 3-azidopropan-1-ol (**11**, 20 mg, 0.198 mmol) were added and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 30 min. The reaction mixture was then cooled to –15 °C and TMSOTf (44 μL, 242 μmol) was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was stirred at –15 °C for 30 min and then at room temperature for 30 min. The reaction was quenched with Et₃N (0.2 mL), the mixture was filtered and concentrated *in vacuo* to provide a crude product. The crude product was purified by column

chromatography, eluting with 20 to 28% EtOAc in hexane to provide product **13** as a light brown syrup (72 mg, 80%). β -Anomer was obtained exclusively.

Procedure C: Ethyl 2,3,4-tri-*O*-benzoyl-1-thio-L-fucopyranoside (**8**, 100 mg, 192 μ mol) was dried by co-evaporation with dry toluene (2 \times 5 mL) and then was dried *in vacuo* for 30 min. The dried compound was dissolved in dry DCM (5 mL) and the flask was purged with argon for 5 min. 4 Å Activated molecular sieves (50 mg) and 3-azidopropan-1-ol (**11**, 29 mg, 288 μ mol) were added and the solution was stirred at room temperature for 30 min. The reaction mixture was cooled to -10 °C. NIS (65 mg, 288 μ mol) and trifluoromethanesulfonic acid (3 μ L, 29 μ mol) were added and the reaction mixture was stirred at -10 °C for 1.5 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to warm to room temperature and was diluted with DCM (20 mL). The reaction was quenched with a saturated solution of Na₂S₂O₃ (5 mL) and filtered. The layers were separated and the organic layer was washed successively with a saturated solution of NaHCO₃ (1 \times 20 mL), water (1 \times 25 mL), and brine (20 mL). The organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated *in vacuo* to provide a crude product. The crude product was purified by column chromatography, eluting with 18 to 25% EtOAc in hexane to provide product **13** as a pale yellow syrup (48 mg, 47%). β -Anomer was obtained exclusively.

Procedure D: 2,3,4-Tri-*O*-benzoyl-L-fucopyranosylbromide (**10**, 100 mg, 185 μ mol) was dried by co-evaporation with dry toluene (3 \times 5 mL). Subsequently, the compound was dried *in vacuo* for 30 min. To the dried compound, dry toluene (5 mL) was added and the flask was purged with argon for 5 min. 4 Å Activated molecular sieves (50 mg) and 3-azidopropan-1-ol (**11**, 19 mg, 185 μ mol) were added and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h. Ag₂O (45 mg, 183 μ mol) was added and a black precipitate formed immediately. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 10 min. The reaction was cooled to 0 °C, trifluoromethanesulfonic acid (8 μ L, 92 μ mol) was added dropwise and the reaction mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 10 min. The reaction mixture was quenched with Et₃N (0.2 mL) and the mixture was filtered through celite, which was thoroughly washed with DCM (2 \times 25 mL). The filtrate was washed with water (2 \times 25 mL). The organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated *in vacuo* to provide a crude product. The crude product was purified by column chromatography, eluting with 20 to 28% EtOAc in hexane to provide product **13** as a pale yellow syrup (60 mg, 58%). β -Anomer was obtained exclusively.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.13 – 8.07 (m, 2H), 8.00 – 7.95 (m, 2H), 7.82 – 7.76 (m, 2H), 7.64 – 7.58 (m, 1H), 7.56 – 7.35 (m, 7H), 7.25 – 7.20 (m, 2H), 5.77 – 5.69 (m, 2H, H-2, H-4), 5.56 (dd, J = 10.5, 3.5 Hz, 1H, H-3), 4.75 (d, J = 7.9 Hz, 1H, H-1), 4.13 – 4.02 (m, 2H, H-5, O-CH₂ linker), 3.68 – 3.60 (m, 1H, O-CH₂ linker), 3.33 – 3.20 (m, 2H, CH₂-N₃ linker), 1.97 – 1.72 (m, 2H, CH₂ linker), 1.36 (d, J = 6.4 Hz, 3H, CH₃). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 166.0, 165.8, 165.5, 133.6, 133.5, 133.4, 130.2 (2C), 129.9 (2C), 129.8 (2C), 129.5, 129.4, 129.0, 128.7 (2C), 128.6 (2C), 128.4 (2C), 101.7 (C-1), 72.2 (C-3), 71.2 (C-4), 70.0 (2C, C-2, C-5), 66.7 (O-CH₂ linker), 48.0 (CH₂-N₃ linker), 29.1 (CH₂ linker), 16.5 (CH₃). MS (ESI⁺): calculated

for $C_{30}H_{29}O_8N_3Na^+$ 582.5 $[M+Na]^+$; found m/z (%) 582.2 (100) $[M+Na]^+$. HRMS (ESI⁺): calculated for $C_{30}H_{29}O_8N_3Na^+$ 582.1842, found 582.1847 $[M+Na]^+$.

4.2.3 3-Azidopropyl- β -L-fucopyranoside (1)

Procedure A: 2,3,4-Tri-*O*-acetyl-1-*O*-(3-azidopropyl)- β -L-fucopyranoside (**12**, 220 mg, 589 μ mol) was dissolved in dry methanol (15 mL). MeONa (162 mg, 3.0 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 16 h. The reaction mixture was neutralized with Amberlite resin until the pH was approximately 5–6. The mixture was filtered and the solvent was removed *in vacuo* to provide a crude product. The crude product was purified by reverse phase column chromatography (SepPak column, 1.0 g), eluting with 20 to 30% ACN in water to provide product **1** as a pale yellow syrup (80 mg, 55%).

Procedure B: 2,3,4-Tri-*O*-benzoyl-1-*O*-(3-azidopropyl)- β -L-fucopyranoside (**13**, 400 mg, 715 μ mol) was dissolved in dry methanol (15 mL). MeONa (162 mg, 4.2 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 16 h. The reaction mixture was neutralized with Amberlite resin until the pH was approximately 5–6. The mixture was filtered and the solvent was removed *in vacuo* to provide a crude product. The crude product was purified by reverse phase column chromatography (SepPak column, 1.0 g), eluting with 30 to 40% ACN in water to provide product **1** as a pale-yellow syrup (95 mg, 54%).

The ¹H NMR spectrum agrees with the literature.²⁵ ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 4.27 – 4.10 (m, 1H, H-1), 3.93 (dt, J = 10.0, 6.0 Hz, 1H, O-CH₂ linker), 3.67 – 3.63 (m, 2H, H-5, O-CH₂ linker), 3.61 (dt, J = 2.8, 1.2 Hz, 1H, H-4), 3.54 – 3.43 (m, 4H, H-2, H-3, CH₂-N₃ linker), 1.88 (p, J = 6.5 Hz, 2H, CH₂ linker), 1.29 (d, J = 6.5 Hz, 3H, CH₃). ¹³C NMR (151 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 104.9 (C-1), 75.1 (C-2), 73.0 (C-4), 72.3 (C-3), 71.9 (C-5), 67.5 (linker C–O), 49.4 (linker C–N₃), 30.3 (linker CH₂), 16.7 (CH₃). MS (ESI⁺): m/z (%): calculated for $C_9H_{17}O_5N_3Na^+$ 270.1, found 270.1 (100) $[M+Na]^+$. HRMS (EI): m/z calculated for $C_9H_{17}O_5N_3Na^+$ 270.1060, found 270.1058 $[M+Na]^+$.

4.2.4 3-Aminopropyl- β -L-fucopyranoside (14)

3-Azidopropyl- β -L-fucopyranoside (**1**, 80 mg, 0.32 mmol) was dissolved in *tert*-butyl alcohol (4 mL) and then argon was purged through a solution for 5 min. Palladium on carbon (10%, 15 mg) was added and hydrogen gas was purged through the reaction mixture over a period of 5 min. The reaction mixture was stirred under hydrogen atmosphere at room temperature for 18 h. The reaction mixture was filtered through celite, which was then thoroughly washed with *tert*-butyl alcohol (2 \times 10 mL). The filtrate was concentrated *in vacuo* to provide product **14** as a pale yellow syrup (68 mg, 95%). The ¹H NMR spectrum agrees with the literature.³⁸ The compound was not stable in solution. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 4.19 – 4.17 (m, 1H), 3.91 (dt, J = 10.0, 6.0 Hz, 1H), 3.66 – 3.58 (m, 3H), 3.49 – 3.43

(m, 4H), 1.90 – 1.82 (m, 2H), 1.27 (d, $J = 6.5$ Hz, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 104.9 (2C), 92.2, 75.1, 73.0, 72.2, 71.9, 67.4, 30.3, 16.7. MS (ESI⁺): calculated for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_5\text{NH}^+$ 222.1 [M+H]⁺, found m/z (%) 222.1 (100) [M+H]⁺. HRMS (EI): calculated for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_5\text{NNa}^+$ 244.1155, found 244.1154 [M+Na]⁺.

4.2.5 2-(3-(4-(Aminomethyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazol-1-yl)propyl)- β -L-fucopyranoside (15)

3-Azidopropyl- β -L-fucopyranoside (**1**, 16.0 mg, 65 μmol) and prop-2-yn-1-amine (4.3 mg, 78 μmol) were dissolved in *tert*-butyl alcohol (2.0 mL). Sodium ascorbate (4.5 mg, 23 μmol) was dissolved in water (2.0 mL) and the two solutions were combined. The resulting reaction mixture was purged with argon for 10 min. To the reaction mixture, $\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2$ (2.4 mg, 13 μmol) was added and the solution was stirred under argon atmosphere at room temperature for 24 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated *in vacuo* to obtain a crude product. The crude product was purified by column chromatography, eluting with 45 to 50% ethanol + NH_4OH (3:1) in DCM to obtain pure amine **15** as a pale yellow syrup (12 mg, 61%). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 8.03 (s, 1H), 4.58 (td, $J = 6.8, 1.7$ Hz, 2H), 4.20 – 4.17 (m, 1H), 4.08 (br s, 2H), 3.85 (ddd, $J = 10.1, 6.3, 5.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.68 – 3.56 (m, 3H), 3.54 – 3.46 (m, 4H), 2.24 – 2.14 (m, 2H), 1.26 (d, $J = 6.5$ Hz, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CD_3OD) 125.2, 104.8, 75.1, 73.9, 73.0, 72.3, 71.9, 66.6, 64.4 (2C), 31.4, 16.8. MS (ESI⁺): calculated for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_5\text{N}_4^+$ 303.3 [M+H]⁺, found m/z (%) 303.2 (100) [M+H]⁺. HRMS (ESI⁺): calculated for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_5\text{N}_4^+$ 303.1664, found 303.1663 [M+H]⁺.

4.3 Fucosylation of carbohydrate acceptor 16 and synthesis of Lewis X fragments

4.3.1 1-(3-Azidopropyl)-2,3,4-tri-*O*-benzoyl- α -L-fucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 3)-2-acetamido-2-deoxy-4,6-*O*-benzylidene- β -D-glucopyranoside (18)

Ethyl 2,3,4-tri-*O*-benzoyl-1-thio-L-fucopyranoside (**9**, 100 mg, 192 μmol) and 3-azidopropyl 2-acetamido-4,6-*O*-benzylidene-2-deoxy- β -D-glucopyranoside (**16**, 113 mg, 288 μmol) were dried by co-evaporation with dry toluene (2 \times 5 mL) and then were dried *in vacuo* for 30 min. The dried compounds were dissolved in dry DCM (5 mL) and the flask was purged with argon for 5 min. 4 Å Activated molecular sieves (50 mg) were added and the solution was stirred at room temperature for 40 min. The reaction mixture was cooled to -78 °C. NIS (65 mg, 288 μmol) was added and the mixture was stirred for 20 min. Afterwards, trifluoromethanesulfonic acid (2.5 μL , 29 μmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 15 min at -78 °C. The reaction mixture was gradually warmed up and at -5 to 5 °C the reaction was completed according to TLC. The reaction mixture was diluted with DCM (20 mL) and filtered. Et_3N (0.2 mL) was added and the filtrate was concentrated *in vacuo* to provide a crude product. The crude product was purified by column chromatography, eluting with 70 to 80% EtOAc in DCM to provide product **18** as a pale yellow crystalline solid (67 mg, 41%). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.12 – 7.99 (m, 2H), 7.79 – 7.73 (m, 4H), 7.67 – 7.59 (m, 1H), 7.55 – 7.34 (m, 9H), 7.25 – 7.19 (m, 2H), 7.13 – 7.02 (m, 2H), 5.91 (d, $J = 6.9$ Hz, 1H, NH), 5.77 – 5.63 (m, 2H, Fuc H-4, H-2), 5.49 (dd, $J =$

10.4, 3.5 Hz, 1H, Fuc H-3), 5.12 (s, 1H, CH-Ph), 5.09 (d, $J = 8.3$ Hz, 1H, GlcNAc H-1), 5.02 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H, Fuc H-1), 4.54 (dd, $J = 10.1, 9.0$ Hz, 1H, GlcNAc H-3), 4.27 (dd, $J = 10.3, 4.8$ Hz, 1H, GlcNAc 5-CH₂), 4.15 – 4.01 (m, 1H, Fuc H-5), 3.99 – 3.88 (m, 1H, linker O-CH₂), 3.66 – 3.57 (m, 2H, linker O-CH₂, Fuc H-5), 3.49 (td, $J = 9.7, 4.8$ Hz, 1H, GlcNAc H-5), 3.43 – 3.31 (m, 3H, GlcNAc H-4, linker CH₂-N₃), 3.23 (ddd, $J = 10.1, 8.3, 6.9$ Hz, 1H, GlcNAc H-2), 2.00 (s, 3H, NAc), 1.90 – 1.78 (m, 2H, linker CH₂), 1.33 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 3H, Fuc CH₃). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) 171.2, 166.0, 165.8, 165.6, 137.2, 133.7, 133.4, 133.2, 130.0, 129.9, 129.7, 129.4, 129.3, 129.0, 128.8, 128.6, 128.5, 128.4, 128.3, 126.0, 101.6 (Fuc C-1), 101.1 (CH-Ph), 100.9 (GlcNAc C-1), 81.8 (GlcNAc C-4), 75.5 (GlcNAc C-3), 72.2 (Fuc C-3), 71.2 (Fuc C-4), 70.0 (Fuc C-2), 69.7 (Fuc-C5), 68.8 (GlcNAc 5-CH₂), 66.7 (linker O-CH₂), 66.0 (GlcNAc C-5), 57.5 (GlcNAc C-2), 48.3 (linker CH₂-N₃), 29.2 (linker CH₂), 23.9 (NHAc), 16.6 (Fuc CH₃). MS (ESI⁺): calculated for C₄₅H₄₇N₄O₁₃ 851.3 [M+H]⁺, found m/z (%) 851.3 (100) [M+H]⁺. HRMS (ESI⁺): calculated for C₄₅H₄₇N₄O₁₃ 851.3133 [M+H]⁺, found 851.3134 [M+H]⁺.

4.3.2 1-(3-Azidopropyl)- α -L-fucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 3)-2-acetamido-2-deoxy- β -D-glucopyranoside (2)

Compound **18** (32 mg, 38 μ mol) was dissolved in 80% aqueous acetic acid (1.0 mL) and the solution was stirred at 80 °C for 1.5 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated to dryness to obtain a crude product. The crude benzylidene-deprotected compound was purified by column chromatography, eluting with 10% methanol in DCM to provide the product as a brown syrup. The obtained intermediate was dissolved in dry methanol (10 mL), MeONa (108 mg, 2.0 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 16 h. The reaction mixture was neutralized with Amberlite H⁺ resin until the pH was approximately 5–6 and the reaction mixture was filtered. The filtrate was concentrated *in vacuo* to obtain a crude product. The crude product was purified by reverse phase column chromatography (SepPak column, 1.0 g), eluting with 40 to 50% ACN in water to provide product **2** as a pale yellow solid (11 mg, 26 μ mol). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 4.43 (d, $J = 8.1$ Hz, 1H), 4.33 (d, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.88 (dt, $J = 9.9, 5.6$ Hz, 1H), 3.80 (dd, $J = 12.0, 2.3$ Hz, 1H), 3.71 – 3.34 (m, 9H), 3.35 – 3.27 (m, 2H), 3.27 – 3.20 (m, 2H), 1.90 (s, 3H), 1.81 – 1.65 (m, 32), 1.21 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 173.8, 106.6, 102.6, 85.3, 77.5, 75.2, 73.1 (3C), 72.0 (2C), 67.2, 62.5, 56.0, 30.1, 23.4, 17.0. MS (ESI⁺): calculated for C₁₇H₃₁N₄O₁₀ 451.2 [M+H]⁺, found m/z (%): 451.2 (100) [M+H]⁺. HRMS (ESI⁺): calculated for C₁₇H₃₁N₄O₁₀ 451.2035 [M+H]⁺, found 451.2027 [M+H]⁺.

4.3.3 1-(3-Aminopropyl)- α -L-fucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 3)-2-acetamido-2-deoxy- β -D-glucopyranoside (19)

Compound **2** (35 mg, 78 μ mol) was dissolved in *tert*-butyl alcohol (5 mL) and then argon was purged through the solution for 5 min. Palladium on carbon (10%, 10 mg) was added and hydrogen gas was purged through the reaction mixture over a period of 10 min. The reaction mixture was stirred under

hydrogen atmosphere at room temperature for 16h. Afterwards, the reaction mixture was filtered through celite, which was thoroughly washed with *tert*-butyl alcohol (2 × 10 mL). The filtrate was concentrated *in vacuo* to provide product **19** as a pale yellow syrup (10 mg, 30%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, D₂O) δ 4.54 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 4.47 (dd, *J* = 7.7, 1.5 Hz, 1H), 3.95 (dt, *J* = 11.2, 5.8 Hz, 1H), 3.89 (dd, *J* = 12.4, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 3.79 – 3.56 (m, 9H), 3.48 – 3.40 (m, 2H), 3.41 – 3.31 (m, 1H), 2.84 (t, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 1H), 2.01 (d, *J* = 2.0 Hz, 3H), 1.81 (p, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 2H), 1.22 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 173.8, 106.6, 102.3, 85.3, 77.5, 75.2, 73.1 (3C), 72.1 (2C), 67.2, 62.5, 56.0, 30.1, 23.0, 15.1 MS (ESI⁺): calculated for C₁₇H₃₃N₂O₁₀ 425.2 [M+H]⁺, found *m/z* (%): 425.2 (100) [M+H]⁺. HRMS (ESI⁺): calculated for C₁₇H₃₃N₂O₁₀ 425.2128, found 425.2130 [M+H]⁺.

Author contribution

R.C. and K.J. synthesized the molecules. H.D. performed NMR structural analysis. J.L. evaluated the affinity for DC-SIGN. P.M. and C.R. supervised the work. P.M., J.L., and C.R. wrote the manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

The following are the Supplementary data to this article: [link](#)

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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